

IMPACT OF LONG-TERM MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE ON SOIL PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES IN NSUKKA, SOUTHEAST NIGERIA

Asadu, C.L.A* and C.E. Ude-Okoro

Department of Soil Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

Corresponding Email: charles.asadu@unn.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17306289>

Keywords:

Solid wastes, soil physicochemical properties, agricultural productivity.

Abstract: *This study was carried out to assess the impact of long-term (above 10 years) municipal waste disposal sites on soil physicochemical characteristics and also on heavy metal concentration on the surface (0-20cm) and sub-surface (20-40cm) depths of the dump sites comparing them with those from non-dump sites within the study locations. The research was conducted at Edem Nru, Owerre-Eze Orba and Obukpa, all less than two kilometres from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Twenty-four (24) cylindrical core and auger soil samples were collected at the same depth intervals in the dump and non-dump sites of the three locations. The results obtained showed that among the particle sizes, clay content at 20-40 cm depth was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at the non-dump site than at the dump site, saturated hydraulic conductivity at 0-20 cm depth was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at non-dump site than at the dump site, bulk density at 0-20 cm depth was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower at the dump site than at non-dump site but at 20-40 cm depth it was the reverse, total porosity at 0-20 cm depth was less at dump site than at non-dump site but at 20-40 cm depth it was the reversed. At the surface (0-20cm) depth; soil pH, available phosphorus and cation exchange capacity were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at dump sites but total N was lower while at the sub-surface (20-40cm) depth; organic carbon, exchangeable acidity, cation exchange capacity, exchangeable calcium and magnesium were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at the dump sites. Only Pb and Zn contents were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at the dump sites and at 0-20 cm depth. Thus, long term dumping of municipal solid wastes appeared to have influenced soil chemical properties positively in the areas and may improve the agricultural productivity of the soils.*

INTRODUCTION

Management of solid wastes is a major environmental problem in many urban and suburban communities in Nigeria.

Traditionally, the soil and water bodies have been at the receiving end of these wastes (Marshall *et al.*, 1996). Municipal solid waste is the most ubiquitous and socially important

Asadu, C.L.A and C.E. Ude-Okoro

contributor of waste and comprises the waste produced by individuals and households as well as industries in urban, suburban or rural communities. Municipal solid waste may comprise both liquid and solid wastes arising from households, business outlets, institutions (schools, hospitals, universities, etc.), street sweepings and non-hazardous solid waste from industries (Getahun *et al.*, 2012, Iorhemen *et al.*, 2016). Proper management of these wastes will minimize the human and environmental health risks associated with them. Hence, the need to regulate its storage at point of generation, collection and transportation, treatment (recycling) and ultimate disposal. Generation of municipal solid waste, together with the high organic proportion in it results in extensive ecological pollution, mainly based on the emission of methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) that contribute to the greenhouse effect. However, municipal wastes particularly the organic fraction may enhance soil fertility and improve the physical properties of soils (Piccolo and Mbagwu, 1997). When such benefits are carefully monitored to supply the crop fertilizer needs, it may reduce the cost of crop production. Furthermore, decayed and composted wastes can enhance soil fertility (Ogunyemi *et al.*, 2003).

Municipal solid wastes can have significant negative effects including foul smells or air pollution, the spreading of diseases and pathogens, soil-enrichment of heavy metals and nitrate loading from liquid wastes (Helmore and Ratta, 1995). Heavy metals are significant environmental pollutants and their toxicity is a problem of increasing significance for

ecological, nutritional and environmental reasons (Jaishankar *et al.*, 2013; Nagajyoti *et al.*, 2010). Heavy metals enter the surroundings by natural means and through human activities. Various sources of heavy metals include soil erosion, weathering of the earth's crust, mining, home effluents, sewage discharge, insecticides and herbicides applied to crops, and many others (Morais *et al.*, 2012). As environmental quality and food production are of major concern in modern societies, a better understanding of the behavior of elements in the air–soil–plant-system seems to be particularly significant (Voutsas *et al.*, 1996). It has been reported that soils differ in their response to organic waste amendments and that it is important to investigate more closely the influence of these organic and inorganic wastes on a range of soil physicochemical properties (Mbagwu, 1989). Waste-amended soils have been reported to have high organic matter content (Anikwe, 2000). Continuous disposal of municipal solid wastes on soils may increase heavy metal concentration and cause harmful effects on soils, crops and human health (Smith *et al.*, 1996).

There is generally not a strong relationship between the concentrations of heavy metals in soil and plants, because it depends on many factors such as soil metal bioavailability, plant growth and metal distribution to plant parts (Voutsas *et al.*, 1996). It is argued that the levels of heavy metals and other particulate matter in municipal solid wastes are low (Anikwe, 2000) but long-term dumping of municipal wastes with the possibility of increasing toxicity of potentially hazardous wastes is of great concern

to urban and sub-urban dwellers. This current study evaluated the impact of solid wastes dumping for over ten years on soil physicochemical properties and heavy metal accumulation in Nsukka, southeast Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Site Description

The study was carried out in suburban areas of Nsukka, the town hosting the University of Nigeria, Enugu state in southeastern Nigeria (Fig. 1). Nsukka is located on latitude $06^{\circ}52' N$ and longitude $07^{\circ}24' E$ with an elevation of 447 m above sea level. Nsukka Local Government Area (LGA) is bounded on the north by Kogi State, on the south by Igbo-Etiti LGA, on the west by Uzo-Uwani LGA and on the east by Udenu LGA.

Climate

The area has a humid tropical climate with wet (April - October) and dry (November - March) seasons in normal years. Precipitation averages 1550 mm per year, with the highest temperatures during the day time reaching $31^{\circ} C$ while the lowest at night dip to $21^{\circ} C$ (Asadu, 2002). The relative humidity varies between 70% and 80% (Oko-Ibom and Asiegbu, 2006).

The range dips below 60% during the harmattan; a 3-week period of foggy, dry weather that occurs between December and January (Asadu *et al.*, 2001).

Field Procedures

Site selection

Three municipal waste dump sites were selected after reconnaissance visits. The study locations were generally flat to slightly undulating with slight rill to no sign of erosion. The study sites included Edem- Nru, Owerre-Eze Orba and Obukpa Layout communities in Nsukka (Table 1). These sites are less than two kilometer from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus and have been used for more than 10 years for dumping municipal solid wastes. At each site, the unsorted municipal wastes mainly made up of household and industrial wastes including leaves and food remnants, paper, rags, plastic/polyethene, tins and metals, bottles, glasses, laboratory wastes and a variety of miscellaneous materials were dumped regularly at each site. The refuse dump areas have grown larger over the years. The coordinates were obtained with a handheld GPS.

Table 1: The Coordinates and location of the dump sites

Location 1; Edem Nru, Nsukka.			
Dump Site			
S/N	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude
1.	6°51'20.96"N	7°25'50.91"E	471.18m
2.	6°51'21.08"N	7°25'50.68"E	470.18m
Non-Dumpsite Site			
3.	6°51'21.62"N	7°25'50.48"E	471.30m
4.	6°51'21.37"N	7°25'50.12"E	471.28m
Location 2; Owerre-Eze Orba, Nsukka			
Dump Site			
5.	6°51'44.61"N	7°25'25.95"E	451.29m
6.	6°51'44.52"N	7°25'26.05"E	450.39m
Non-Dumpsite Site			
7.	6°51'43.57"N	7°25'26.09"E	452.19m
8.	6°51'43.85"N	7°25'26.71"E	451.49m
Location 3; Obukpa Layout, Nsukka			
Dump Site			
9.	6°52'45"N	7°24'18"E	415.00m
10.	6°52'45"N	7°24'18"E	413.30m
Non-Dumpsite Site			
11.	6°52'42"N	7°24'16"E	420.50m
12.	6°52'42"N	7°24'17"E	420.50m

It was a common practice of urban/suburban dwellers to cultivate a variety of crops in parts of the temporarily abandoned sections of the dump sites because of lush green vegetation found around those dump sites. Beside these three locations, are well established farmlands where cassava (*Manihot esculanta*), plantain

(*Musa paradisiacal*), cocoyam (*Colocasia esculenta*), Banana (*Musa acuminata*), yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*), fluted pumpkin (*Telfaria occidentalis*), okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) and maize (*Zea mays*) are often cultivated.

Figure 1: Map of Nsukka area showing the locations of the study area

Asadu, C.L.A and C.E. Ude-Okoro

Sample Collection

Soil samples were collected from the three dumpsites after removing the wastes. Four auger soil samples at depth intervals of 0-20 and 20-40cm were collected giving a total of 12 samples. The same number of auger soil samples was collected at the non-dump sites situated 50 meters away from the dumpsites; giving the overall total of 24 samples. Twenty-four cylindrical core soil samples were also collected at the same depth intervals in the dump and non-dumpsites at the three locations. The soil samples were analyzed in the Research Laboratory of the Department of Soil Science and the Central Science Laboratory, University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN).

Soil Analysis

The auger samples were air-dried under laboratory condition, gently crushed with a pestle and sieved with a 2 mm sieve to obtain the fine-earth fractions. The particle size distribution was determined on the fine-earth fraction by the Bouyoucous hydrometer method (Day, 1965). The percent sand, silt and clay obtained were traced on a soil textural triangle to determine the soil textural class.

The hydraulic conductivity of saturated soils (K_{sat}) was determined by the constant head method of Klute and Dirksen (1986). This method is based on the direct application of Darcy's equation to a saturated soil column of uniform cross-sectional area. A hydraulic head difference as imposed on the soil column, and the resulting flux of water measured using the relation:

$$K_s = \frac{V L}{At (H_2 - H_1)}$$

Where,

V = Volume of water that flows through the sample of cross sectional area (A) in time (t).

$(H_2 - H_1)$ = Hydraulic head difference

L = Length of sample

The following properties were determined by the method of Obi (2000)

The bulk density was determined by calculation after oven drying soil at 105 °C for 48 hours or to constant weight, using the relation:

$$Bd = \frac{\text{Oven dry mass of soil} \times 100}{\text{Volume of soil}}$$

Volume of soil in cylinder was determined by using the formula; $\pi r^2 h$.

Where, π is a constant with value of 22/7

r^2 = square of the internal radius of the core

h = height of core.

The soil pH was determined in a soil to liquid ratio of 1:2.5 using a glass electrode pH meter Soil Survey Staff (SSS, 2014). The Walkley-Black modified acid-dichromate procedure was used to determine organic carbon using diphenol amine as an indicator and potassium dichromate as the oxidizing agent as outlined by SSS (2014). Total N was determined by the macro-Kjeldahl digestion method through the careful use of a macro-Kjeldahl digestion-distillation apparatus (SSS, 2014). Available P was determined by the Bray II extraction procedure (SSS, 2014). Exchangeable acidity was obtained by leaching the soil samples with $BaCl_2$ -triethanolamine (TEA) solution buffered at pH 8.2 (SSS, 2014). Cation exchange capacity (CEC) by NH_4OAc at pH 7.0 was obtained by saturating the soil exchange sites with an index cation (NH_4^+) at pH of 7.0 by treating the soil with 1 M NH_4OAc at pH 7.0

and the concentration of NH_4^+ in the extract was determined by distillation and titration (SSS, 2014). The percentage base saturation was calculated by expressing the sum of exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K and Na) as a percentage of CEC by ammonium acetate at pH 7.0 (SSS, 2014).

Heavy Metals

Available heavy metals (copper, lead, cadmium and chromium) content of the soil samples were obtained using a flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer (C. E 3000, Thermo Scientific, Germany) filled with deuterium lamp for background checking

Statistical analysis

The data obtained from the physical and chemical analysis were subjected to a T-test using a statistical package for the Social Science Software 2015 version to compare the soil physical and chemical properties of the dump sites with those from the non-dump sites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Physical Properties of Dump and Non-Dump Site Soils

The physical properties of 0-20cm and 20-40cm depths obtained from both the dump and non-dump site soils (Table 2) showed that the textural classes were the same, sandy clay loam (SCL). This is an indication that the solid waste did not affect the texture of the soils significantly. It is known that soil textures hardly change over years with amendment application (Asadu et al., 2008a). Even the particle size distribution was not affected except the clay content at 20-40 cm depth that was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) at the non-dumpsite. This is the normal situation in

tropical soils where eluviation/illuviation of clay is not disrupted. It is important to note that although sandy loam texture has been recommended by Loughry (1973) as being suitable for waste disposal sites, soils with greater than 700 g/kg sand are highly unsuitable for waste disposal because they are highly permeable and allow large quantities of leachates to pass through the soil. Similarly, soils with clay and silt concentrations greater than 310 g/kg are unsuitable for waste disposal because they encourage surface flooding and potential pollution from surface runoff (Loughry, 1973).

The saturated hydraulic conductivity (KSat) which was significantly lower in the dump site surface soil compared to the non-dump site tended to suggest that the solid wastes could have interrupted normal process of eluviations in the dump site soils. However, the total porosity did not corroborate this finding as it was significantly higher in the non-dump site soils possibly because the total porosity was made up of more of microporosity than macroporosity (transmission porosity) in the dump site soils. Soil porosity represents the percentage of the total soil volume occupied by pores spaces. According to Hillel (1998), porosity values typically range from 30% to 60% for mineral soils, with higher values indicating better aeration and water movement. It shows that the soils in the dump sites may be better aerated than non-dump site soil probably due to air spaces created by organic matter deposits in soils of the dump sites.

Saturated hydraulic conductivity is a measure of how well the soil transmits water under

saturated conditions (Marshall *et al.*, 1996) and higher conductivity implies that the soil in the dump sites transmit water better under saturated conditions when compared to the soil in the non-dump site soils. According to Mbagwu (1989) incorporation of organic wastes

significantly increased soil hydraulic conductivity but the magnitude of increase depended on the rate of application. The generally higher saturated hydraulic conductivity values in the dump site soils imply lower run-off and erosion in soils.

Table 2: Comparison of soil physical properties of dumpsite and non-dumpsites soils

Treatment	Clay	Silt	Sand	Texture	KSat	Bulk density	Total porosity
	(g/kg)				(cm/hr)	(g/cm ³)	%
Surface depth (0-20cm)							
Dump site	266	146	588	SCL	3.98	1.89	28.9
Non-dump site	266	153	581	SCL	21.97	1.57	41.3
LSD(P<0.05)	Ns	Ns	Ns		*	*	*
Sub-surface (20-40 cm)							
Dump site	296	213	491	SCL	2.06	1.84	30.6
Non-dump site	336	160	504	SCL	1.93	1.88	29.3
LSD(P<0.05)	*	Ns	Ns		Ns	*	*

Note: KSat = Saturated hydraulic conductivity, LSD = Least Significance Difference (* = $p \leq 0.05$, Ns = Not significant).

The bulk density (BD) was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at 0-20cm depth at dump site compared to non-dump site but significantly lower at the 20-40 cm depth (Table 2). This trend clearly indicated that the impact of the solid waste was more at the 0-20 depth. This might be associated with the weight of the waste causing possible compaction. Bulk density is a measure of soil compaction, with higher values indicating more compacted soils. According to Brady and Weil (2008), typical BD values for mineral soils range from 1.0 to 1.6 g/cm³ and values above 1.6 g/cm³ may indicate compaction, while values below 1.0

g/cm³ are often found in organic soils. The BD values obtained indicated moderate compaction except in 0-20 cm depth of the non-dump site soils. This may be because organic and inorganic materials in the municipal wastes help to increase the soil matrix thereby reducing soil bulk density in 0-20 cm depth of the non-dump site soils. Similar findings were made by Mbagwu (1992). Lower bulk density is a positive productivity indicator in a clayey soil as it helps in easing root penetration and therefore also will encourage downward movement of water through old root channels (Obi, 2000).

Chemical Properties of Dump and Non-Dump Site Soils.

The soil pH obtained at 0-20 cm soil depth was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at dump site than at non-dump site (Table 4). This was the same trend for the CEC and available phosphorus but the reverse was the case for total nitrogen (Table 4). At 20-40 cm soil depth, organic carbon and exchangeable acidity values were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at the non-dump site locations while CEC, exchangeable Ca and Mg values were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at dump site locations (Table 4). The EA levels provide an indication of potential soil acidity and nutrient leaching in the soils. The pH values indicated acidic to neutral soil conditions. According to Brady and Weil (2008), soil pH plays a crucial role in nutrient availability, microbial activity, and potential toxicity of heavy metals. Soils with pH below 6.5 are generally considered acidic and may require liming to raise the pH for optimal growth of some plants. The total N values were generally moderate in both soils especially at the 0-20 cm depth, thus the soils would

respond to nitrogen application for optimal crop growth. According to Havlin *et al.*, (2014), soils with total N above 0.05% are considered fertile and suitable for agricultural purposes.

All the CEC values were above 6 cmol/kg but below 12 cmol/kg. According to Hazelton and Murphy (2007), soils with CEC below 6 cmol/kg are considered low in fertility while values above 12 cmol/kg are considered high. Thus, both soils were of moderate in fertility status. The values of exchangeable cations obtained were not significantly affected by the solid waste dumping even though higher values were obtained at the dump site locations which may be of an advantage to crops. Exchangeable nutrient cations play crucial roles in soil fertility, plant nutrition and soil structure.

The available P values were all below 100 mg/kg. According to Munson and Trolove (2007), soil P concentrations above 30 mg/kg are considered adequate for plant growth, while levels above 100 mg/kg may indicate excessive phosphorus inputs, potentially leading to environmental concerns.

Table 4; Mean effect of surface (0-20cm) and subsurface (20-40 cm) depths between dumpsite and non-dumpsites soils on soil chemical properties

Treatment	pH	OC	TN	Av. P	Exc Acidity	CEC	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺
		(g/kg)	(mg/kg)					(cmol/kg)		
Surface (0-20cm) depth										
Dump site	6.7	1.54	0.03	88.14	1.53	10	2	2	0.06	0.12
Non-dump site	5.6	1.46	0.04	25.18	2.6	7	1.4	0.9	0.05	0.1
LSD(P<0.05)	*	Ns	*	*	Ns	*	Ns	Ns	Ns	Ns
Subsurface (20-40 cm) depth										
Dump site	6.7	0.87	0.04	14.46	1.2	9.6	1.5	1.6	0.04	0.08
Non-dump site	6.3	1.23	0.1	17.72	2.9	7.2	0.7	0.5	0.04	0.09
LSD(P<0.05)	Ns	*	Ns	Ns	*	*	*	*	Ns	Ns

Note: pH = *pondium hydrogenis*, OC = organic carbon, TN = total nitrogen, Av. P = available phosphorus, CEC = cation exchange capacity, exchangeable, LSD = Least Significance Difference (* = p ≤ 0.05, Ns = Not significant).

Heavy metal concentration of the various study sites

The heavy metal contents from the soils of both the dump and non-dumpsite locations at

0-20cm and 20-40cm depths were statistically the same except that of lead and zinc which were significantly higher at the dump site at the 0-20 depth (Table 6).

Table 6; Mean effect of surface (0-20cm) and surface (20-40cm) depths between dump and non-dumpsite soils on soil heavy metal contents

Treatment	Pb	Cd	Zn	Cr
(mg/kg)				
Surface (0-20cm) depth				
Dump site	0.2	0.03	1.16	1.05
Non-dumpsite	0.11	0.03	0.27	1.02
LSD(P<0.05)	*	Ns	*	Ns
Subsurface (20-40cm)				
Dump site	0.14	0.03	0.18	1.19
Non-dumpsite	0.07	0.02	0.3	1.17
LSD(P>0.05)	Ns	Ns	Ns	Ns

Note: Pb = Lead, Cd = Cadmium, Zn = Zinc, Cr = Chromium, LSD = Least Significance Difference (* = $p \leq 0.05$, Ns = Not significant).

The lead (Pb) content was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at dump site than at non-dumpsite at 0-20cm depth. According to Kabata-Pendias (2011), typical Pb concentrations in unpolluted soils range from 10 to 30 mg/kg, with a crustal abundance of 15 mg/kg. The values obtained were generally lower than these ranges, indicating relatively low levels of lead contamination in the studied soils. The soil cadmium and Chromium contents were not affected by solid waste dumping. According to Kabata-Pendias (2011), typical Cd concentrations in unpolluted soils range from 0.01 to 1mg/kg, with a crustal abundance of 0.1 mg/kg. The values obtained were either within or below this range, suggesting minimal cadmium contamination in the studied soils. The low cadmium concentrations may be attributed to various factors, such as the geological origin of the soil, the absence of significant anthropogenic

sources of cadmium contamination, or the presence of soil properties that limit cadmium mobility and bioavailability (Naidu *et al.*, 1997). According to Kabata-Pendias (2011), typical chromium concentrations in unpolluted soils range from 5 to 120 mg/kg, with a crustal abundance of 100 mg/kg. The values obtained were relatively low, suggesting minimal chromium contamination in the studied soils. The low chromium concentrations in the soils may be attributed to low content in the parent materials of the soils, the absence of significant anthropogenic sources of chromium contamination, or the presence of soil properties that limit chromium mobility and bioavailability (Chuan *et al.*, 1996)

The soil zinc (Zn) content was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher at dump site locations especially at 0-20cm depth. According to Kabata-Pendias (2011), typical Zn concentrations in unpolluted soils range from

10 to 300 mg/kg, with a crustal abundance of 70 mg/kg. The observed values were within the lower limit of this range, indicating relatively low levels of zinc in the studied soils.

Based on the values obtained which were within the tolerable limits in agricultural soils, the solid wastes had not impacted negatively on the soils. The results appeared to agree with those of Asadu et al (2008b) who worked on the impact of sewage sludge on soils within the same location.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study was carried out to assess the impact of long-term municipal solid waste on soil physicochemical properties in Nsukka, Enugu state, Nigeria. The mean values of saturated hydraulic conductivity, bulk density and porosity from the dump site locations were lower compared to their corresponding values from the non-dump sites, particularly at the

REFERENCES

Anikwe, M. A. N., (2000). Amelioration of a heavy clay loam soil with rice husk dust and its effect on soil physical properties and maize yield. *Bioresources Technology* 74, 169–173.

Asadu C. L. A. (2002), Fluctuation in the characteristics of an essential short tropical season, 'August Break' in Eastern Nigeria. *Discovery and Innovation* 14(1/2):92-101.

Asadu C. L. A, Ucheonye-Oliobi C. and Agada C (2008) Assessment of sewage application in southeastern Nigeria 1: Impact on selected soil

surface (0-20cm) depth. The mean soil pH values from the locations were mostly in the acidic range (below 6.5) and the soils from dump site locations showed elevated levels of organic carbon, total nitrogen and available phosphorus. The concentration of heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr) and zinc (Zn) were generally within the typical ranges for unpolluted soils. Generally, the values obtained were within the tolerable limits in agricultural soils in the area indicating that the solid wastes had not impacted negatively on the soils. However, monitoring of soil properties and heavy metal contents at dumpsite locations at least every five years is recommended in order to avert the negative impact of soil contamination, compaction and degradation, which can affect soil quality, groundwater and human health.

morphological and physical properties. *Outlook on Agriculture* 37 (1) 57-62.

Asadu C. L. A, Ukadike B. and Agada C (2008b) Assessment of sewage application in southeastern Nigeria II: Impact on soil chemical properties, trace and heavy metal accumulation in soil and underground water. *Outlook on Agriculture* 37 (1): 63- 69.

Asadu C. L. A., Ekwo A. U and Udigwe T. K. (2001), Soil characteristics around Lake Opi in eastern Nigeria and land use recommendations. *Agro-Science Journal*, 2(1). 76-90.

- Brady, N. C. and Weil, R. R. (2008). The nature and properties of soils (14th ed.) Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Chuan, M. C., Shu, G. Y. and Liu, J. C. (1996). Solubility of heavy metals in a contaminated soil; effects of redox potential and pH. *Water, air and soil pollution*, 90(3-4), 543-556.
- Day, P. R., (1965). Particle size analysis. In C. A. Black (ed) *Laboratory Methods*. In: Klute, A., Ed., *Methods of Soil Analysis. Part 1: Physical and Mineralogical Methods*, 2nd Edition, Agronomy Monograph No. 9, ASA, Madison, 687-734.
- Getahun, T., Mengistie, E., Haddis, A., Wasie, F., Alemayehu, E., Dadi, D., Van Gerven, T. and Van der, B. (2012). Municipal solid waste generation in growing urban areas in Africa: current practices and relation to socioeconomic factors in Jimma, Ethiopia. *Environmental Monitoring and assessment*. 184: 6337 - 6345.
- Havlin, J. L., Tisdale, S. L., Nelson, W. L., and Beaton, J. D. (2014). *Soil fertility and fertilizers* (8th ed). Pearson.
- Hazelton, P., and Murphy, B. (2007). *Interpreting soil test results; what do all the numbers mean?* (2nd edition). CSIRO Publishing.
- Helmore, K., Ratta, A., (1995). The surprising yields of urban agriculture. *Choices, the Human Development Magazine of UNDP* 4 (1), 1995.
- Hillel, D., Warrick, A. W., Baker, R. S. and Rosenzweig, C. (1998). *Environmental Soil Physics*. Academic Press. New York.
- Iorhemen, O. T., Alfa, M. I. and Onoja, S. B. (2016). The review of municipal solid waste management in Nigeria: the current trends. *Advances in Environmental Research*, 5(4): 237-249
- Jaishankar M, Mathew B. B, Shah M. S, Gowda K. R. S. (2014). Biosorption of Few Heavy Metal Ions Using Agricultural Wastes. *Journal of Environment Pollution and Human Health*. 2014; 2(1):1–6.
- Kabata-Pendias, A. (2011). *Trace elements in soils and plant* (4th ed.) CRC Press, Boca Raton.
- Klute, A. and Dirksen, C. (1986). *Hydraulic Conductivity and Diffusivity: Laboratory Methods*. In: Klute, A., Ed., *Methods of Soil Analysis. Part 1: Physical and Mineralogical Methods*, 2nd Edition, Agronomy Monograph No. 9, ASA, Madison, 687-734.
- Loughry, F.G. (1973). The use of soil science in sanitary land-fill selection and

- management. *Geoderma* 10, 131–139.
- Marshall, T. J., Holmes, J. W., Rose, C. W., (1996). *Soil Physics*, third ed. Cambridge University Press, UK.
- Mbagwu, J. S. C., (1989). Influence of cattle feed lot manure on aggregate stability, plastic limit and water relations of the soil in North central Italy. *Biological Wastes* 28, 257–269.
- Mbagwu, J. S. C., (1992). Improving the productivity of organic and inorganic amendments. Part 2. Changes in physical properties. *Bioresources Technology* 42, 167–175.
- Mo., L. S., Moo, C.C. and Ho, Y. S. (1999). Specification of Cd, Cu and Zn in sewage sludge treated soils incubated under aerobic conditions. *Agric. Chem. Biotechnology*. 42:85–91.
- Morais S, Costa F. G. and Pereira M. L. (2012). Heavy metals and human health. In: Oosthuizen J, editor. *Environmental health – emerging issues and practice*. 2012. pp. 227–246.
- Munson, C., and Trolove, S. (2007). Interpretation of Soil Test Reports for Plant Requirements. *Crop & Food Research Confidential Report* No. 1846.
- Nagajyoti PC, Lee KD, Sreekanth TVM. Heavy metals, occurrence and toxicity for plants: a review. *Environ Chem Lett*. 2010; 8(3):199–216.
- Naidu, R., Kookana, R. S., Summer, M. E., Harter, R.D., and Tiller, K. G. (1997). Cadmium sorption and transport in variable charge soils; A review. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 26(3), 602-617.
- Obi M. E. (2000). *Soil Physics. A compendium of lectures*. Allanto publishers Nsukka, pp. 13-17.
- Ogunyemi S, Awodoyin RO, Opadeji T (2003). Urban agricultural production: heavy metal contamination of *Amaranthus cruentus* L. grown on domestic refuse landfill soil in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Emir. J. Agric. Sci*. 2003.15(2): 87-94.
- Oko-Ibom, G. O and Asiegbu J.E (2006). Growth and yield responses of rainy season field tomatoes to fertilizer application timing and splitting. *Journal of environmental sciences. Toxicology and food technology (IOSR-JESIFT)* 6, 39-49.
- Piccolo, A. and Mbagwu, J. S. C., (1997). Exogenous humic substances as conditioners for the rehabilitation of degraded soils. *Agro-Food- Industry Hi-Tech*. March/April 1997.

Smith, C. J., Hopmans, P. and Cook, F.J. (1996). Accumulation of Cr, Pb, Cu, Ni, Zn and Cd in soil following irrigation with untreated urban effluents in Australia. *Environmental Pollution* 94, 317–323.

Soil Survey Staff (SSS). (2014). Kellogg soil survey laboratory methods manual. Soil Survey Investigations Report No. 42, Version 5.0. R. Burt and Soil Survey Staff (ed.). U.S Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service. P. 1001.

Voutsas, D., Grimanis, A. and Samara, C. (1996). Trace elements in vegetable grown in an industrial area in relation soil and air particulate matter. *Environmental Pollution* 94, 325–335.